

**OPPORTUNITIES TO USE THE EXPERIENCES OF GREAT BRITAIN IN
IMPLEMENTATION OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS IN
UZBEKISTAN**

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G'afforov Ibrohimjon Qobiljon o'g'li
Student National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract: *This article will tell you about the advantages of using British experiences in the development of science in Uzbekistan, in particular, about the high interest and demand for scientific research in this country. We bring to your attention the facts about the quality of education in the United Kingdom, which has an average IQ of 100, and by this result has surpassed the United States of America, a large and modern continent.*

Keywords: *nominal GDP, Google, Microsoft, PepsiCo, clinical pharmacologist.*

The global power of each country is closely related to its army, natural resources, economy and, most importantly, its scientific potential. Just to connect this point with an interesting fact about India, India is the world's fastest growing trillion-dollar economy, with a nominal GDP of 2.94 trillion. is considered In 2019, India ranked fifth in terms of economy, surpassing Great Britain and France. The country's gross domestic product is 11.33 trillion in terms of purchasing power parity. rated as In addition, the main managers of the world's largest companies and projects are also considered to be of Indian origin. We can think of people like Sundar Pichai, CEO of Google, Satya Nadella, CEO of Microsoft, or Indra Nooyi, CEO of PepsiCo [<https://www.viralindiandiary.com/indian-ceos-international-companies-networth/>]. Therefore, today the power of the countries is

assessed through the scientific potential. Based on this, the high demand for education and innovation and the high attention paid to it by the President and the government indicate how important these sectors are. This requires a comprehensive analysis of the content of education, the process of training applicants, teaching staff, information and methodological support, educational technologies and scientific activities [Левшина В.В. Развитие методологии создания системы менеджмента качества вуза// Ж. Университетское управление. –2003, No 2. С. 1.].

It is known from history that Europe experienced a scientific revolution in the 17th century. Because philosophers began to base their theories on experiments and observations instead of accurate measurements. During this period, mathematics and astronomy were the fields of science that led the scientific revolution, and the royal palaces were among the major patrons of these sciences. Although the European Union was founded in 1993, there is a long tradition of invitation and action for scientific research in Europe. Europe is home to some of the world's oldest universities, such as the University of Bologna, which prioritizes education based on philosophy, theology, and law rather than the specific sciences. Also, in the period after the Second World War, science and technology played an increasingly important role in the lives of Europeans.

As we mentioned at the beginning of our opinion, research and development in Great Britain is very important in the universities of the United Kingdom. Therefore, many in the country establish science parks to facilitate cooperation with production and industry. In particular, between 2004 and 2012, Great Britain produced 6% of the world's scientific research works and accounted for 8% of the share of scientific citations.

Great Britain is one of the countries that receives the most funds for research from the European Union. Between 2007 and 2013, the UK received a total of €8.8 billion for research, development and innovation in EU member states. At the time, it was considered the largest share in the European Union. In addition, the

European Research Council funded 79 projects in the UK in 2017, more than any other EU country. On the plus side, the UK was ranked fourth in the Global Innovation Index 2020, 2021 and 2022.

The UK Government's Science Office is a science advisory group within the UK government. The organization advises the UK government on policy and decision-making based on science and long-term thinking. It is chaired by the government's chief scientific adviser, Patrick Vallance, a British physician, scientist and clinical pharmacologist who has worked in both academia and industry [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Patrick_Vallance]. Since 2018, he has been working as the chief scientific adviser to the UK government.

This office works in collaboration with the Science and Research Group, which funds research through research councils. Together, they create and promote guidelines and frameworks that describe how the natural and social sciences, engineering, and medicine can be used to promote policy sustainability. This office promotes and supports the use and management of citizen science, and encourages them to adapt to best practices across the country and, where appropriate, abroad. Notably, each government agency has its own Chief Scientific Advisor and they work together on mutual issues and develop the strategic development of the enterprise or agency. In some cases, the government's chief scientific advisor collaborates with other advisors to the government to find solutions on important interrelated issues. In doing so, they often bring in top national and international scientists to help with the matter and ensure that their advice is as reliable as possible.

In conclusion, it is permissible to say that our compatriot Sadrijahan Hasanov, who is studying at the University of Law in Great Britain, said in an interview in "Yangi O'zbekiston" newspaper, "One of the biggest factors in the development of English people's love of books. Another thing that caught my attention is the distribution of daily issues of local publications on public transport and I can say that before the end of the day the newspapers run out.

In addition, the British rely more on facts than empty and lofty words. What is said here has no power if it is not based on numbers and statistics. The main thing is that development projects, whether in the state or in the private sector, are long-term. For example, if you ask a person working in a government job what he is busy with, he will say that he is busy with the implementation of projects developed 5-6 years ago. This is ingrained in the character of the people of the country”, he said, which shows how demanding and thirsting for knowledge the British people are [<https://yuz.uz/uz/news/buyuk-britaniyaning-taraqqiyot-omillari-inglizlar-xarakteriangliyada-tahsil-olayotganhamyurtimiz-bilan-suhbat>] [To‘xtasinov N. “Yangi O‘zbekiston” gazetasi// “Yangi O‘zbekiston” va “Pravda Vostoka” gazetalari tahririyati» DUK. -2020, 3-sentabr. 1-b.]. Therefore, by creating a “British atmosphere” in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is possible to introduce such initiatives in our country, increase the prestige of the country and accelerate its development. And the fact that personnel work according to their specialties leads to a relative reduction of shortcomings or errors in that field. Although it will take many years and hard work to fully adapt to such experiences and understand their true essence, it will definitely pay off in the near future.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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